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IMPACT OF GOVERNMENT ENDEAVORS ON MARKETING INDIAN TOURISM

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ABSTRACT

In this particular paper, researcher discusses about government endeavors in Indian tourism marketing and analyzes its impact in growth of Indian Tourism Marketing. Researcher has included the journey of development of Indian tourism from ancient time to present. She has an appropriate data and she has used co-integration test for testing hypothesis. Results indicate that there is significant impact of amount allocated on tourism in five years plans on tourist arrival in India. This paper may be significant for the Indian tourism marketing, especially for growth of tourism marketing and it helps in growth of nation.

Keywords: Endeavor, Tourism, Marketing, Tourism destinations

INTRODUCTION

Tourism comes from the word “tour”. It can be defined as travelling, comparatively peaceful and fresh natural areas with the specific objects admiring, enjoying the scenery, business purpose and studying. The tourism sector in India is very significant for accelerating growth of the country and due to tourism industry India has become one of the most important international destination. American Marketing Association, Chicago, 1960 Committee define Tourism in these words,

“Tourism denotes the temporary short term movement of people to destination outside the place where they normally live and work and their activities during their stay at these destinations.”

Burkart, A.J. and Medlik S. define tourism in the “tourism past present and future, 1988 on the page no.195,

“Tourism is a study of demand for and supply of accommodation and supportive services for those staying away from home and the resultant patterns of expenditure, income creation and employment.”

Tourism in India has registered amazing growth in the last decade. The Indian government plays a key role in growth of tourism. Government decided to increase revenues from the tourism sector by projecting India as the ultimate tourist spot.

NEED OF THE STUDY

As we know that India has unique climates at different places, clam features and all types of tourism. It is famous for its culture & hospitality services. It has 24 world heritage monuments and 6 natural sites. Repair and maintenance for these sites is essential for sustainable growth of Indian tourism. This is the basic thought of this study to know the government endeavors for Indian tourism.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study about the government endeavors for Indian tourism.
2. To analyze the impact of government endeavors on Indian tourism.

HYPOTHESIS

H_0 = There is no significant impact of amount allocated on tourism in five years plans on tourists arrival in India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is an empirical research. It is based on secondary data and data has been collected from official websites of planning commission of India, annual reports of Ministry of Tourism and concern books, journals, & websites etc. In this way the collected information has been analyzed by co-integration test.

Research Methodology	
Sources of Data	Books , journals, websites
Types of Information	Number of Tourists arrival in India & amount allocated on tourism in five years plans of India
Time period	1951 to 2012 (five years plans)
Analysis	Co-integration Test

TOURISM BEFORE INDEPENDENCE

India is one of the most beautiful tourism destinations. It is known for its natural beauty, calm, culture, heritage monuments and hospitality. In the early days, pilgrimage or pilgrim travel had “great importance. Ashoka the great travelled” different places for spreading the doctrines of Buddha. He travelled from “Pataliputra to Lumbini on to Kapilavastu and Sarnath and finally to Gaya. Emperor Ashoka left his memories at each spot and rest houses where travelers could rest. He planted trees along the road sides for the protection of traveler from the harsh sun shine. Harshvardhan was another great emperor who gently influenced by the Buddhist scriptures, built institutions and Dharamshalas for the travelers. Rest houses were built in towns and villages. A number of monasteries were also built for the pilgrims. This shows that travel facilities were much improved” in that time. In those days Brahmin villages and Monasteries were famous for attracting scholars and monks.

There is lack of evidence that who was first foreign visitor of India but he/she was a Persian because there is much evidence of “caravans of Persians visiting India”, in the inscriptions dating to the reign of the “Persians King Darius”. Evidences also reveal exchanges of trade, commerce and cultural between India and Persia. During the reign of “Chandragupta Maurya, Persian customs have been practiced in the courts. Hieun-tsang”, a Chinese tourist came to India in 633AD for collecting and translate ancient Buddhist scriptures.

It is said that when Alexander the Great came to India, he found well maintained roads covered with shady trees. Marco Polo was another traveler, who passed through India on his way back from China. All travelers of the world were much interested in seeing India. India was a rich and prosperous country in those days. Mark Twain said,

“... Of splendor and rags..... There is only one India..... The one land that all men desire to see and having seen once by even a glimpse..... Will not give that glimpse for the shows of the rest of the world put together....”

During the rule of the Mughals, the emperors travelled extensively and contributed in tourism. Lots of monuments were constructed by the Mughals. With the fall of the Mughal empires, there was a downfall in trade and commerce. It reduced the mobility of the people, except pilgrimages. The sea side resorts hill stations and spas which were the centers of recreation and pleasure were hardly used by the early medieval period. Over the years, however the scenario changed and a complex character of tourism emerged. The growth of modern technology, rising income and improved facilities contributed to the emergence of modern tourism.

Government Endeavors for Indian Tourism

As researcher said above that India is one of the most beautiful tourism destinations but unfortunately it has to say that tourism did not figure as a subject in constitution of India and

there is no amount allocated in first five years plan of India. In second five year plan tourism became a part of constitution and government allocated Rs. 3.36 crore.

In third five year plan government was set up a corporation in 1966 ITDC (Indian Tourism Development Corporation) for development of infrastructure and promotion of India as a tourism destination.

In fourth and fifth Plan government focused on development of these tourism destinations like Kovalam, Gulmarg, Goa, Kullu-Manali etc. and also focused on development of Cultural Tourism like Buddhist Centers and heritage monuments in India through master plans.

The Sixth Plan was a major landmark in the history of Indian Tourism because in this plan first 'Tourism Policy' was announced during 1982 in the country with the concept of 'Travel Circuit' to provide maximum benefits of tourism.

In Seventh Five Year Plan government set up The National Committee on Tourism in 1986 to evaluate the economic and social relevance of tourism in India and to draw up a long measure for ensuring accelerated growth of tourism and govt. also set up Tourism Finance Corporation of India (T.F.C.I) for financing tourism projects.

In Eighth Plan, first "National Action Plan for tourism" was presented in the Parliament on 5th May, 1992. This action plan was focused on development of "Special Tourism Area" of tourism circuits. 'The Tourism Synergy Programme' was prepared in 1993 and included the activities and infrastructure components that provided by various agencies including the private sector and State Governments. It was further modified and converted into a 'National Strategy for the Development of Tourism' during 1996.

In Ninth Five Year Plan, Expert House status was granted to tourism units for boosting foreign exchange earnings, employment and income generation through tourism activities. Govt. also made effective coordination in Public & Private sectors to achieve synergy in the development of tourism in India. In developing tourism, it was to be ensured that the sites are conserved and the environment is not degraded.

In tenth plan government focused on the employment generating potentials of tourism, creation of world class infrastructure and effective marketing plans and programs. "Incredible India", tourism promoting campaign was launched in 2002.

In eleventh plan government focused on increasing the international visitors, attract higher quality tourists, increasing per head spending and reduce the seasonality in international tourists arrival promote MICE tourism also encourage medical tourism. One ongoing scheme of this plan was up gradation of information system and uses of IT in tourism development; this scheme was started in tenth plan and continued in eleventh plan.

In twelfth plan government set same objectives of tenth and eleventh plan and continued all scheme with improvement. In this plan government focused on development of skillful manpower in tourism.

ANALYSIS

For this study researcher uses secondary data released on the official website of Ministry of Tourism and Planning Commission of India. Researcher uses co integration test for testing hypotheses. Following table reveals the amount allocate on tourism and number of tourists arrival in India.

Five Years Plan	Years	Amount Allocate in Crores	Number of Tourists Arrival in India
First Five Years Plan	1951-56	0	48763
Second Five Years Plan	1956-61	3.36	74332
Third Five Years Plan	1961-66	4	145248
Forth Five Years Plan	1969-74	25	537271
Fifth Five Years Plan	1974-79	23.62	716403
Sixth Five Years Plan	1980-85	72	785136
Seventh Five Years Plan	1985-90	138.68	922022
Eighth Five Years Plan	1992-97	272	1005750
Ninth Five Years Plan	1997-2002	486	1240000
Tenth Five Years Plan	2002-07	2900	1761500
Eleventh Five Years Plan	2007-12	5156	2793000

Source: Ministry of Tourism & Planning Commission of India

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.880432	21.50526	15.49471	0.0055
At most 1	0.233256	2.390423	3.841466	0.1221
Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesized		Max-Eigen	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.880432	19.11484	14.26460	0.0079
At most 1	0.233256	2.390423	3.841466	0.1221
Max-eigenvalue test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Unrestricted Cointegrating Coefficients (normalized by $b^*S11*b=I$):				
AMOUNT_ALLOCATE_IN_CR	FTA			
-0.018285	1.44E-06			
0.011585	-4.55E-06			

Unrestricted Adjustment Coefficients (alpha):				
D(AMOUNT_ALLOCATE_IN_CR)	-630.0896	-26.96621		
D(FTA)	-91203.94	42744.86		
1 Cointegrating Equation(s):		Log likelihood	-177.8731	
Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)				
AMOUNT_ALLOCATE_IN_CR	FTA			
1.000000	-7.86E-05			
	(2.8E-05)			
Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)				
D(AMOUNT_ALLOCATE_IN_CR)	11.52096			
	(1.95285)			
D(FTA)	1667.631			
	(774.145)			

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

As per the above analysis the hypothesis is rejected therefore there is significant impact of amount allocated on tourism by the government on number of tourists arrived in India. These are the following reasons:

- This amount is helpful in repairing and maintenance of tourism destinations.
- It is also helpful in development and improves the service quality of Transportation, Accommodation and other services.
- Information technology also plays a vital role in improvement of service quality especially in the field of communication.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

On the basis of above study researcher has concluded that all the activities that were done (making plans & policies and their executions in tourism) by the government gave a positive results. She observed that number of tourists is increased year by year and it’s all due to endeavors of government. Tourism is an information based industry and transfer of information is occurred rapidly and 4G of internet launched in India for improving communication system.

Apart from this there are many tourism sites that depict our rich culture but the maintenance of such sites are not as good as required like; Rakhigarhi, Haryana- The Largest city in the Indus Valley Civilization. And there are many Nature Parks that need to keep maintained. Ministry of tourism should inspect maintenance of tourism sites regularly and properly.

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